

**Department for International Development
(Innovate UK)**

Data management plan required?	Yes
RDM policy Link	No
Definition of data	Not specified
Length of data management plan	Not specified
DMP template/ requirements	Not specified
Required data repository	Yes. Outputs and associated metadata should be deposited in R4D. Use of subject-based or institutional repositories is also recommended.
Time for data release	Raw or derived datasets should be deposited within 12 months of final data collection.
Time for long-term storage of data	Minimum of five years after project completion
Costings	Associated costs to be budgeted for.
Last updated	1 st November 2012
Contact Details	support@innovateuk.gov.uk
Comments	N/A

Documents used:

General guidance for grant applicants <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/innovate-uk-funding-general-guidance-for-applicants>

Accessed: May 2018